

The Effect of Leadership Style on Nurse Job Satisfaction, Mediated by Empowerment and Commitment

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ABSTRACT

The hospital institution is one of the most important public institutions that play an important and vital role in achieving development and social balance. The aim: of this study is to determine the effect of leadership on job satisfaction, on the Commitment of nurses and on empowerment, and determine the effect of empowerment on job satisfaction and determine the effect of commitment on job satisfaction in hospital PKU Muhammadiyah Gamping. This study is a qualitative research survey study, a sample of 57 nurses working in the hospital was obtained. A questionnaire tool was used to collect the information with nurses is presented using a Likert scale size guide. This study uses SPSS validation test and conducting path analysis. The findings of this study have shown that factors that can affect nurses' job satisfaction are leadership and empowerment, commitment. The findings suggest that nursing leaders in hospital acute settings can enhance the nursing work environment by practicing appropriate leadership styles and empowering strategies, including greater participation of nursing staff in the decision making process. Ultimately, more effective nursing management should result in improved nursing staff retention, job satisfaction, and work commitment.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Empowerment, Job satisfaction, Commitment

I. INTRODUCTION

Considering that the hospital institution is one of the most important public institutions that play an important and vital role in achieving development and social balance, with the curative, hospital, and preventive care it provides to members of society, its success and raising the efficiency of its members depends on the effectiveness of the human element in it. The work includes incentives, human relations, and care for workers in accordance with their desires that satisfy their needs, leaving positive effects and creating a sense of satisfaction for them towards work. Leadership style is of great importance on job satisfaction and work environment, and to the motivation and performance of professionals. The nurses are satisfied and motivated in their work environment they have the ability to reward their organization with the ability to provide better quality care and increase retention [1]. This study, used leadership theory to develop and test a model that links leadership to nursing perceptions of empowerment, performance, job satisfaction, and nurses Commitments. When employees are not working, organizational leadership style may be defective. Therefore, there is a need for organizations to adopt leadership styles that are in line with employee empowerment which will increase the company's performance in the long run [2].The purpose

of this research is to know the effect of leadership on job satisfaction, commitment, and empowerment, through the effect of commitment and empowerment on job satisfaction as a result of the absence of many studies on job satisfaction for nurses.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative research survey study, it is done through questionnaires with nurses. Population is Nurses at hospital PKU Muhammadiyah Gamping, a total of 57 nurses.

III. RESULTS

The respondents' background Of the 57 responses. Results show that majority of the respondents are female nurses (80.7%) and only (19.3%) male nurses.

Table 1. Validiy Test

No	Variable	Corrected item – total correlation	R table	Conclusio n
1	Leadership style	.427-.845	.2162	Valid
2	Job satisfaction	.402-.785	.2162	Valid
3	Commitment	.424-.664	.2162	Valid
4	Empowerment	.441-.796	.2162	Valid

Table 2. Reliability Test

No	Variable	Cronbach alpha	Conclusion
1	Leadership style	.949	Reliable
2	Job satisfaction	.877	Reliable
3	Commitment	.854	Reliable
4	Empowerment	.789	Reliable

HYPOTHESIS:

- H1: The affect leadership on job satisfaction**
- H2: The effect of leadership styles on the Commitment of nurses**
- H3: The effect of empowerment on job satisfaction.**
- H4: The effect of commitment on job satisfaction**
- H5: The effect of leadership styles on empowerment.**

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing

HYPOTHESIS	The probability value	The R square value	An effect
H1	0.056	0.065	25%
H2	0.286	0.021	14.4%
H3	0.008	0.120	34.6%
H4	0.058	0.064	25, 2%
H5	0.356	0,016	12.5%

IV. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the impact of leadership style on job satisfaction, nurses' commitment, and empowerment, determine the impact both of nurse commitment and empowerment on job satisfaction. The impact of leadership styles on empowerment and job satisfaction and nurse commitment is important for nursing managers and leaders, in order to create a work environment that encourages and facilitates a high level of commitment among the nursing staff. This is particularly important, especially in the wake of the current challenges facing healthcare systems in relation to the shortages of health professionals, especially among nursing professions.

1. The effect of leadership style on job satisfaction. Leadership style doesn't have much effect on job satisfaction, value of the leadership style variable is 0.056, that is mean leadership variable has an effect of 25% on satisfaction leadership style has a positive and significant effect on burnout, burnout had a significant effect on job satisfaction, leadership style had a significant effect on job satisfaction, and burnout also mediated the effect of leadership style on job satisfaction [3].
2. The effect of leadership styles on the Commitment of nurses. Leadership style doesn't have much effect on Commitment of nurses, value of the leadership variable is 0.286 that means leadership variable has an effect of 14.4% on commitment. Leadership styles and psychological empowerment significantly affect commitment levels, the Transformational, Transactional and Laissez-faire styles positively affect commitment levels, with the Transformational style having a marginal effect, the results reveal that autonomy is the only component of the psychological empowerment construct that significantly affects commitment levels. that nursing leaders in hospital acute settings can enhance the nursing work environment by practicing appropriate leadership styles and empowering strategies, including greater participation of nursing staff in the decision making process, more effective nursing management should result in improved nursing staff retention, job satisfaction, and work commitment.
3. The effect of leadership style on empowerment The empowerment variable has a significant effect on satisfaction, the probability value of the empowerment variable is 0.008, which means the empowerment variable has an effect of 34.6% on satisfaction. The nurse managers feel structurally and psychologically empowered when working in a supportive environment with a clear mission, tasks, and values. Empowerment is more likely to be perceived when there is an appropriate organizational culture in the workplace, health-care organizations that do not provide a working environment that empowers nurse managers might meet a significant degree of turnover at this administrative position. The findings revealed that team-level differences of variation on culture were greater than those seen at an organization level. The assessment of organizational culture might be considered an important feature for an organization to reach optimal operational performance. Thus, differences in culture offer possibilities to look for new ways of organizing work in hospitals and supporting health-care workers [4].
4. Nurse commitment has implications for job satisfaction The variable commitment has an effect on satisfaction but is not significant, the probability value of variable commitment is 0.058, which means that the satisfaction of the variable has an effect of 25, 2% on commitment. Professional commitment of nurses contributes positively to job satisfaction with nurses. The measure of professional commitment for nurses should be included in psychosocial

causal models linking baseline self-assessment and job satisfaction, indicating the need for activities in professional training interventions designed to influence low levels of professional commitment in nurse behavior

5. Empowerment has an effects on job satisfaction

The leadership variable has not a significant effect on empowerment, the probability value of the leadership variable is 0.356, which means that the empowerment variable has an effect of 12.5% on leadership.

A link has been made between nursing and organizational and career outcomes, such as job satisfaction [5], autonomy [6], confidence [7], respect [8], fatigue and tired [9], and keenness to stay at work [10]. Longitudinal studies showed that nurses' information on empowerment anticipated fatigue, tiredness, and job satisfaction over time [5].

Empowerment is likely to be seen when there is a climate in the workplace and an appropriate organizational culture. Therefore, a significant degree of turnover in a managerial position may be achieved when health care institutions do not provide a work environment that enables nursing managers [11].

The leader plays a more important role in handing over responsibility than focusing on leadership and authority when dealing with subordinates [12]. Also, leaders' behaviors, attitudes, characteristics may contribute and skills to a good leadership style in the organization [1]. A best leader can lead employees to perform to their full potential [13]. Leaders must have the ability to work efficiently, honestly and impartially, and communicate clearly with employees [14]. Effective leadership style often completes the assigned task [15]. The right leadership style satisfies the employee, which is an excellent indicator of a better approach that may lead the employee to work more actively [16]. Leaders must be able to communicate the message, values, and vision of their organizations in order to encourage employees [17]. The leader is also someone who can guide the behavior of his employees [18].

In our study, nurses perceive themselves to have good levels of empowerment, low levels of job satisfaction and commitment. These findings suggest nurses may feel less motivated when they perceive that their work has no significant value to the organization, and important aspects of their job, work environment, and patient care. This may be experienced as burnout or apathy and the nurses' sense that they are exerting too much effort with too little reward or return. The empowerment was the only statistically significant predictor of commitment, suggesting that nurse managers have and authentic commitment to full engagement of the nurses in appropriate decision-making about patient care processes, patient safety and their working environment. This finding is inconsistent with literature showing that increased participation empowerment facilitates greater commitment. In this context, (Kara et al., 2013) noted that if management does not allow for staff participation in decision-making, the effort to empower frustrates employees, resulting

in an increased dependence on authoritarian structures. Thus, the study results suggest that nurse managers tend to focus more on nurse compliance and task completion, emphasize assignments, work standards, and task-oriented goals. Our research shows how empowerment has a positive correlation with job satisfaction. Different leadership styles exist because people are, by nature, different in their traits, characteristics, and communication abilities. It is therefore important for a leader to understand when a particular style must be demonstrated or avoided. Moreover, the results reveal that most studies analyzed more than one leadership style at the same time. This reflects the need to produce research which, by investigating on a broad spectrum, allows light to be shed on a topic that is still largely empirically based and with little robust scientific evidence. The fact that more than one style of leadership has led to positive outcomes amongst healthcare staff, in terms of job satisfaction, is proof that different cultures, contexts, and individuals require styles and approaches that vary over time, according to circumstances.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study have shown only the effect of empowerment on job satisfaction has a significance effect with probability value of the empowerment variable is 0.008. The probability value of the empowerment variable is smaller than the significance value of 5% or less than 0.05, which means that the empowerment variable has a significant effect on satisfaction. Also the leadership do not have a significant effect on each of the independent variables on job satisfaction, on the Commitment and on empowerment, the commitment do not have a significant effect on job satisfaction, this is because the distribution of data is still insufficient.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

In study did not measure the effect of leadership styles on the management level, as future studies may examine this topic. Additionally, future research may also explore how sub-dimensions of leadership influence job satisfaction through organizational commitment.

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